

Microwave-assisted synthesis: Paradigm of Green Chemistry

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Microwave (MW) synthesis is considered as an efficient approach towards "Green and sustainable chemistry" because it is environmental-friendly in nature. This synthetic process is less time consuming because it uses MW as an alternative energy source. The benefits of MW synthesis include rapid heating, absence of inertia, ease of use, better homogeneity in temperature with the transfer of energy into the whole reaction medium without superficial heating. This review focuses on the utilization of microwave irradiation technique in the synthesis of organic compounds and to present the advantages of microwave synthesis.

Keywords: Microwave, synthesis, Green Chemistry, heterocyclic compound.

1. Introduction

Microwave assisted synthesis involves the use of microwave radiation to conduct chemical reactions and organic synthesis. Microwave is a form of electromagnetic energy that falls at the lower frequency end of the electromagnetic radiation. Microwaves are a group of electromagnetic energy with a frequency range of 300 to 300,000 Megahertz (MHz) and wavelengths of 1 m to 1 mm. This frequency range falls just above the radio waves and below the visible light in the electromagnetic spectrum. All domestic microwave ovens operate at 2.45 GHz which is one of a few permitted frequencies regulated to avoid interference with e.g. RADAR and telecommunication applications and also because this frequency has the right penetration depth for laboratory experimental conditions. Beyond 30 GHz, the microwave frequency range overlaps with the radio frequency range^{1,2}.

2. Mechanism of microwave in heating

Within the microwave frequency range, the electric field component interacts with polar molecules which results in dielectric heating³. Microwave energy consists of an electric field and a magnetic field, though only the electric field transfers energy to heat a substance. Magnetic field interactions

do not usually occur in chemical synthesis. Microwaves move at the speed of light (300,000 km/s). The energy in microwave photons is very low about 0.037 kcal/mol which is very low relative to the typical energy required to cleave chemical bonds which require about 80–120 kcal/mol. As a result microwave radiation would not affect the structure of an organic molecule. In the excitation of molecules, the effect of microwave absorption is purely kinetic. Microwaves interact with polar and ionic species most easily. The substances attempt to align themselves with the electric current being created by the microwaves. Loss tangent is used to determine how easily microwaves heat a substance. The equation used is:

$$\tan \delta = \epsilon''/\epsilon'$$

where ϵ'' is the dielectric loss, or the ability of the substance to convert electromagnetic radiation into heat, and ϵ' is the dielectric constant or the ability of the polar molecule to align itself with the electric field⁴. Essentially, the higher the value for the loss tangent, the better the molecule absorbs microwave energy. Therefore, for syntheses with microwave radiation, this information is important when choosing solvents and reactants. If neither the solvent nor any reactant absorbs

microwave energy, they are transparent to it; the reaction mixture will not be heated. However, if either the solvent or reactants absorb microwave energy, heating of the reaction mixture will occur relatively easily. The interesting thing is that it only takes one, either the reactants or the solvent, to absorb the microwave energy. This is because as one heats up, it causes everything it is touching to heat up as well, thus heating the entire reaction mixture by convection. One large advantage this has over traditional heating methods is, with microwave radiation, the energy is being applied directly to the system. Traditionally, heat was applied through hot water baths, heating mantles, sand baths, or some other means that requires that the container holding the substances be heated first in order for their contents to be heated. In fact with microwave chemistry, it is preferred that the reaction container not be heated. This is because it would require some of the microwaves to interact with the substance the container is made from, when they could simply pass through and interact with the reactants or solvent directly^{5,6}.

3. Use of Microwave technology in organic synthesis

The ability of MW-assisted organic synthesis to rapidly synthesize organic compounds is of significant benefit for compound library generation. Moreover, it allows modifications in selectivity (chemo, regio, and stereo-selectivity) and solvent, catalyst free conditions⁴ (Fig. 1). The synthesis of heterocyclic compounds have major role in medicinal chemistry research, from the past few decades; many significant advances in practical aspects of organic chemistry have included novel synthetic strategies and methods as well as advent of a vast array of analytical techniques. Hence, the present day chemists are no longer confined to using only thermal energy for driving chemical reactions. With increasing complexity of the problems and the availability of newer methods of activation of chemical reactions, chemist have

restored to using microwave technique for rapid and efficient synthesis of a variety of compounds, because of selective absorption of microwave energy by polar molecules. The application of Microwave irradiation to provide enhanced reaction rate and improved product field in chemical synthesis and further showed the formation of a variety of carbon heteroatom bonds⁷.

The poor solubility of organic reactants in aqueous media is a major limitation for organic synthesis in water, which generally results in immiscible or biphasic reaction mixtures. This problem has been tackled by using surfactants, mixing with co-solvents, heating of the reaction mixture, or grinding of reactants. However, some of these issues have been addressed and solved by designing protocols based on the use of microwaves, ultrasound, or pressure reactors and other benign co-solvents. Reactions in aqueous media are termed as "in-water" and "on-water" reactions, on the basis of the nature of reactants (solubility) during chemical reactions. Higher pressure and temperature attained rapidly in Microwave-assisted processes may help increase the rate of reactions via enhanced homogeneous mixing of the reactants (in-water) and decreasing the hydrophobic effects (on-water)⁸.

4. Microwave-assisted organic synthesis (MAOS)

Now-a-days, several academic and industrial research groups are already using MAOS as a technology for optimization of reaction condition, efficient synthesis of new chemical entities or for discovering and probing new chemical reactivity. The various lead compounds are synthesized by microwave-assisted technique are discussed below.

4.1. Microwave synthesis of five membered heterocyclic rings

4.1.1. Synthesis of pyrrole ring system:

Pyrroles are five membered heterocycles of great impor-

Fig. 1. Importance of microwave-assisted synthesis.

tance because pyrrole is a basic substructure of numerous biologically active alkaloids and pharmaceutical products^{9–11}. Classically, pyrroles were synthesized by various methods viz. Knorr pyrrole synthesis¹², Paal-Knorr synthesis¹³, Hantzsch pyrrole synthesis¹⁴ etc. The classical Paal-Knorr cyclization of 1,4-diketones to give pyrroles is dramatically speeds under microwave irradiation and high yields are obtained. The microwave technique completes the reaction within 2 min while conventional reaction takes 12 min as it involves activation if Lewis acid for the reaction to proceed¹⁵.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of pyrrole ring.

Heating an aniline with 2,5-dimethoxytetrahydrofuran in water (0.64 M) in a MW reactor at 150°C for 30 min resulted in the formation of the corresponding in water in 81–99% yield. Wilson *et al.* reported this simplified approach to the uncatalyzed Paal-Knorr condensation¹⁰.

Scheme 2. Microwave (MW)-induced uncatalyzed reaction.

4.1.2. Synthesis of pyrazole ring system:

Pyrazole and its derivatives have displayed broad spectrum of pharmacological and biological activities. In particular, pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines are useful for treatment of a wide variety of stress-related illnesses¹⁶. Well-known methods for pyrazole synthesis are Pechmann pyrazole synthesis and Knorr pyrazole synthesis¹⁷. Microwaves have been used for the preparation of pyrazoles from hydrazones using the Vilsmeier cyclization method by treatment with POCl₃ and DMF. The reaction is speeded-up by factors of several 100-fold¹⁸.

4.1.3. Synthesis of imidazoles:

Imidazole derivatives have attracted considerable attention in recent years as these are endowed with a wide range of pharmaceutical activities. The application of imidazoles

Scheme 3. Synthesis of pyrazole ring.

as 1,3-disubstituted imidazole salts as ionic liquids are also well known^{19,20}. Classically, imidazoles have been synthesized by various methods. An important classical preparation of imidazoles is from α -diketone, an aldehyde and ammonia. Under Microwave heating at 130 W for 10 min in solvent free condition completes the reaction whereas conventional synthesis by refluxing requires 4 h²¹.

Scheme 4. Synthesis of imidazole derivatives.

Ohta and co-workers performed the synthesis of polysubstituted 2-aminoimidazoles via functionalization of the imidazole ring. O-methyl-iso-urea (1 mmol), acetal or ketal of the α -aminocarbonyl compound (1 mmol) were mixed thoroughly with 1 g of the clay in a glass mortar. The reaction mixture was irradiated under microwave for 10–15 min at 150 W.

Scheme 5. Synthesis of polysubstituted imidazole.

4.1.4. Synthesis of oxazole and oxazoline rings:

The oxazole and 2-oxazoline ring system have demonstrated its vast synthetic potential as a masked carboxylic acid for over a century. Their unique properties serve both as a synthetic precursor and a mediator in a multitude of

chemical processes continue to inspire new scientific application. The preparation of oxazolines shows that partially saturated five-membered rings can also be prepared advantageously using microwaves²².

Scheme 6. Synthesis of oxazoline ring.

4.1.5. Preparation of triazoles:

1,2,3-Triazoles are indispensable structural motifs of compounds with increasing importance in the field of pharmaceuticals, crop protection, and material sciences^{23,24}. Conventional Huisgen's 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition technique proved to be highly versatile in giving substituted 1,2,3-triazoles by the reaction between organic azides and substituted alkynes. Aryl cyanide has been used for preparation of triazoles using microwave irradiation²⁵.

Scheme 7. Synthesis of triazole ring.

4.1.6. Preparation of tetrazoles:

The synthesis of 1,5-disubstituted tetrazoles is carried by reaction between benzanilide (1.01 mmol), phosphorus oxychloride (10.15 mmol) and sodium azide (4.04 mmol). The reaction mixture is subjected to microwave irradiation at 120 W for 2–15 min.

Scheme 8. Synthesis of 1,5-disubstituted tetrazoles.

Tetrazoles has been conveniently prepared by microwave assisted synthesis²⁶.

Scheme 9. Synthesis of tetrazole ring.

4.1.7. Preparation of oxadiazoles:

The dehydration of unsymmetrical diacylhydrazines using Burgess's reagent gives 1,3,4-oxadiazoles rapidly under microwave irradiation condition^{27,28}.

Scheme 10. Synthesis of oxadiazole ring.

4.2. Microwave synthesis of benzo-fused derivatives of five membered rings

4.2.1. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons:

(PAHs) undergo very few cycloaddition reactions. Their only known cycloadditions are with ozone, the Diels-Alder reactions with hexachlorocyclopentadiene, and 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition with the azomethine ylide derived from 1-(4-methoxyphenyl) aziridine-2,3-dicarboxylate. The paucity of cycloadditions with PAHs is not surprising in light of the inherent stability associated with their resonance energy. Recently, PAHs have been shown to react with nitrile oxides under solvent free microwave irradiation to produce fused isoxazolines. As a comparison, the reactions have also been carried out under classical thermal conditions. At high temperature with prolonged heating, both thermal reactions in solution and in the absence of solvent gave very low yields. Performing the reactions neat in a domestic microwave oven operating at 650 W afforded the same products in shorter reaction times and in generally better yields.

4.2.2. Synthesis of benzimidazole, oxazole and thiazole:

Ring closure reactions of appropriate *o*-substituted anilines yields benzimidazoles, benzoxazoles, and

benzthiazoles. The reactions are much faster and in significantly high yield under microwave conditions than conventionally²⁹.

Scheme 11. Synthesis of fused ring.

4.2.3. Synthesis of indole:

Indole nuclei are broadly found in a large amount of synthetic and natural products. Indole is a popular component of fragrances and the precursor to many pharmaceuticals³⁰. Classically, indoles have been synthesized by various methods^{31,32}. The classical Fischer-indole synthesis from an aryl hydrazine and a ketone is speeded up by several 100-fold by microwave synthesis. Microwave synthesis takes only 30 seconds while conventional technique takes 2 h by refluxing method³³.

Scheme 12. Synthesis of indole ring.

4.2.4. Synthesis of γ -carbolines:

The Graebe-Ullmann synthesis which converts 1-arylbenzotriazoles into carbazoles or their heterocyclic analogs is accelerated under microwave conditions where the 1-(4-pyridyl)benzotriazole is converted into a γ -carboline³⁴.

Scheme 13. Synthesis of γ -carbolines.

4.3. Microwave synthesis of six membered heterocyclic rings

4.3.1. Synthesis of dihydropyridines:

The Hantzsch dihydropyridine synthesis remains one of the most important routes to produce pyridine ring systems. Under conventional conditions long periods of heating are required and yields are poor to moderate. Microwaves dramatically reduce the heating times and also significantly increase the product yields³⁵.

Scheme 14. Synthesis of dihydropyridines.

4.3.2. Synthesis of 2-amino-3,5-dicarbonitrile-6-sulfanylpyridines:

The substituted pyridines are prepared via one-pot three-component reaction of aldehydes, malononitrile and thiophenols (molar ratio 1:2:1) in ethanol using KF/alumina as a heterogeneous green catalyst under controlled microwave conditions for 5–10 min with 62–93% yield (Scheme 15).

Table 1. Microwave synthesis of 2-amino-3,5-dicarbonitrile-6-sulfanylpyridines using KF/alumina as green catalyst

Compd. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	Reaction condition			
					Microwave		Conventional	
					Time (min)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	H	H	H	H	5	86	45	71
2	H	H	H	-CH ₃	5	90	40	78
3	H	H	H	-OCH ₃	5	92	30	82
4	H	-OCH ₃	H	H	5	92	35	81
5	H	-OCH ₃	H	-OCH ₃	5	93	30	82
6	H	NO ₂	H	H	10	62	30	56
7	H	Cl	H	H	7	83	70	68
8	Cl	H	H	H	7	81	60	67

Scheme 15. Synthesis of 2-amino-3,5-dicarbonitrile-6-sulfanylpyridines.

Scheme 16. MW-irradiated solvent-free three-component reaction leading to 1,4-dihydropyridines.

4.3.3. Synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridines:

Kuraitheertha kumaran *et al.* reported the synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridines under solvent-free MW-irradiation which involves three-component reaction between β -ketoester, aldehydes and ammonium acetate using lanthanum oxide as a catalyst. This method provides the desired products in excellent yields (90–98%) after short reaction times (40–80 s) in comparison to the classical Hantzsch methods (Scheme 16).

4.3.4. Synthesis of dihydropyrimidines:

The Biginelli reaction is essential for the preparation of dihydropyrimidine derivatives and excellent results are found for reactions carried out with microwave enhancement³⁶.

Scheme 17. Synthesis of dihydropyrimidines.

4.3.5. Synthesis of 5-unsubstituted-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones:

A new series of 5-unsubstituted-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones is synthesized by Biginelli multicomponent reaction under MW-assisted solvent-free conditions which involves three-component, one-pot condensation of an aromatic aldehyde, acetophenone and urea using $ZnCl_2$ as catalyst (Scheme 18).

Scheme 18. MW-assisted solvent-free Biginelli multicomponent reaction leading to dihydropyrimidinones.

4.3.6. Synthesis of tetrazines:

The Diels-Alder reaction between aza-olefins and aza-dicarboxylic ester to give tetrazines is speeded-up by a factor of 1000 by microwave enhancement³⁷.

Scheme 19. Synthesis of tetrazine.

4.4. Microwave synthesis of polycyclic six membered heterocyclic rings

4.4.1. Preparation of quinolone:

Quinoline derivatives occur in various natural products, especially in alkaloids and are often used for the design of many synthetic compounds with diverse pharmacological properties³⁸. A number of methods of quinoline synthesis viz. Skraup, Doebner-von Miller, Friedlander, Pfitzinger, Conrad-Limpach, Combes have been known since the late 1800s³⁹. The Skraup of quinolines when carried out conventionally gives low yields but it has been reported that microwave enhancement reduces the reaction time to a few minutes and allows high yields to be isolated⁴⁰.

4.4.2. Synthesis of 4-quinolinones:

4-Quinolinones are important class of alkaloids which are

Scheme 20. Synthesis of quinolone.

used to treat various infectious diseases. These are the first choice of chemotherapeutic agents for the treatment of bacterial infections. A mixture of aniline (1 eq), ethyl acetoacetate (1 eq), acetic acid (0.01 eq), in diphenyl ether (1 ml) was irradiated with microwave at 300 W for 3–5 min to produce 4-quinolinones.

4.4.3. Synthesis of triazoloquinazolinones:

Triazoloquinazolinones are heterocycles that are of considerable interest because of their diverse biological activities. Triazolo-quinazolinones are produced with good yields within few minutes during the reaction of aromatic aldehydes

Table 2. Synthesis of 4-quinolinones

Comp. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	Yield (%)
1	H	H	-OMe	H	75
2	H	-OMe	H	-OMe	71
3	H	-OCH ₂ CH ₂ O	-OCH ₂ CH ₂ O	H	62

Scheme 21. Synthesis of 4-quinolinones.

Scheme 22. Synthesis of triazoloquinazolinones.

with 5-amino-1(*H*)-1,2,4-triazole and dimedone in DMF under microwave irradiation (Table 3 and Scheme 22).

Table 3. Synthesis of triazoloquinazolinones

Compd. No.	Ar	Conventional heating		Microwave irradiation	
		Time (min)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	30	76	3	95
2	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	60	68	7	95
3	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	40	72	5	92
4	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	90	62	10	94

4.4.4. Preparation of benzimidazo-quinazolinones:

Benzimidazo-quinazolinones is prepared by the reaction of aromatic aldehydes with 2-amino-benzimidazole in DMF with improved yields within few minutes under microwave irradiation (Table 4 and Scheme 23).

Table 4. Synthesis of benzimidazo-quinazolinones

Compd. No.	Ar	Conventional heating		Microwave irradiation	
		Time (min)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	6	65	1	96
2	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	10	70	2	93
3	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	12	72	5	90
4	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	6	72	2	85
5	C ₆ H ₅ -	8	64	3	92

Scheme 23. Synthesis of benzimidazo-quinazolinones.

Scheme 24. Synthesis of tetrahydrobenzo-quinolones.

4.4.5. Synthesis of tetrahydrobenzo-quinolones:

Tetrahydrobenzo-quinolones is synthesized by reaction between 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone, aromatic aldehydes, methyl or ethyl acetoacetate and ammonium acetate in ethanol as solvent. All reactions were performed under microwave irradiation at 120 W, or by classical heating in oil bath for 4 h. This synthetic pathway confirmed that there is significant acceleration of the reaction time under MW (10 min) as compared to the conventional heating (4 h) which leads to the formation of products with high yields (80–89%).

4.4.6. Synthesis of isoquinolines:

Isoquinolines is synthesized under MW-irradiation in the presence of ammonia, but no catalyst was required in this case due to the highly reactive nature of the aldehyde group (Scheme 25). This annulation proceeded regioselectively, through a 6-*endo-dig* mechanism. The mechanism of reaction involves the formation of an imine, subsequent cyclization followed by proton shift.

4.4.7. Synthesis of quinazoline:

2-Aminobenzamide reacts with chloroacetylchloride under MW-activation to produce an intermediate N-(2-aminophenyl)-2-chloroacetamide which further undergoes cyclization to afford 2-chloromethylquinazoline-4(3*H*)-one in basic aqueous media.

Scheme 25. Synthesis of isoquinolines.

Scheme 26. Synthesis of quinazoline.

4.4.8. Microwave synthesis of piperidine:

Ravindran *et al.* described the synthesis of piperidine by condensation of diphenacyl anilines with different arylidene acetophenones in the presence of sodium ethoxide. It involves Michael addition-aldol reaction ring closure reaction

Scheme 27. Synthesis of piperidine via microwave assisted one pot method.

Scheme 28. Synthesis of alkaloid (isolamellarin).

and leads to formation of substituted piperidines in good yields under microwave irradiation for 3 min (Scheme 27).

4.5. Microwave synthesis of alkaloids

4.5.1. Synthesis of benzopyranones and isolamellarin alkaloids:

A simple and highly effective C-O carboxylic coupling reaction catalyzed by copper(I) salts has been developed to synthesize benzopyranones. The reaction of various 2-halo-aryl carboxylic acids was examined using microwave irradiation. A new class of pyrrolo-isoquinoline alkaloid, isolamellarin, was synthesized based on the annulation of dihydro-isoquinoline with aryl pyruvates under basic condition and Cu-mediated/MW-assisted C-O carboxylic lactonization.

4.6. Microwave synthesis of flavonoids

Flavonoids are a group of naturally occurring phenolic compounds widely distributed in the plant kingdom, the most abundant being the flavones. The members of this class of

compounds display a wide variety of biological activity. A simple and rapid method for the synthesis of flavones has been described by Varma *et al.* (Scheme 18) which proceeds via a solid state dehydrative cyclization of *o*-hydroxydibenzoylmethanes in clay micro-environment using microwaves. The synthesis for various substituted flavonoid derivatives are summarized in Table 5.

Scheme 29. Flavanoid synthesis by microwave.

Table 5. Synthesis of flavones via cyclization of *o*-hydroxydibenzoyl-methanes

Comp. No.	R	R ₁	Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	H	H	1.0	75
2	H	Me	1.0	77
3	H	OMe	1.5	76
4	H	NO ₂	1.0	78
5	OMe	H	1.0	73
6	OMe	Me	1.5	80
7	OMe	OMe	1.0	72

4.7. Microwave-assisted synthesis of curcumin analogs

Curcumin is chemically 1,7-diaryl-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-

dinone. It is widely used for the treatment cancer, Alzheimer's disease, HIV and inflammations etc. The synthesis of carbocyclic curcumin analogues has been produced by using microwaves.

4.8. Microwave-assisted synthesis of curcumin derivatives

Curcumin derivatives are produced by reaction between 3-acetyl-2*H*-chromen-2-one, aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile and ammonium acetate under microwave irradiation at 350 W for 6–10 min.

4.9. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 3-aryl-furo[3,2-*c*] coumarins

A solution of 4-hydroxy coumarin (0.002 mol) and 2-aryl-1-nitro-ethenes (0.002 mol) in methanol (5 ml) containing piperidine in catalytic amount was stirred at room temperature for 10 min and then irradiated for 5–7 min in microwave at 240 W (40%) power level.

4.10. Microwave-assisted synthesis of isocurcumin analogs

Isocoumarins is used as synthetic precursors and intermediates for preparation of various medicinal agents. Microwave-assisted one-step synthesis of isocurcumin analogs involves reaction between equimolar amount of 2-formylbenzoic acid and monochloro acetone with good yields (84–87%) at power level 200 W for 15–30 min in presence of base K₂CO₃.

Scheme 30. Microwave-assisted synthesis of curcumin analogs.

Scheme 31. Microwave-assisted synthesis of curcumin derivatives.

Scheme 32. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 3-aryl-furo[3,2-*c*]coumarins.

Scheme 33. Microwave-assisted synthesis of isocurcumin analogs.

Table 6. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 3-aryl-furo[3,2-*c*] coumarins

Comp. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	Reaction condition	
				Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	H	H	H	5.5	69
2	CH ₃	H	H	6.0	67
3	H	CH ₃	H	5.5	70
4	Cl	H	H	5.0	65
5	H	H	CH ₃	5.5	69

4.11. Synthesis of 1,8-dioxo-octahydroxanthene

A mixture of 5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione (2 mmol), aldehyde (1 mmol) and [cmmim][BF₄] (200 mg) was subjected to microwave irradiation at 40% power level (280 W) for suitable time to produce 1,8-dioxo-octahydroxanthenes. The synergy of microwave and catalyst-free methodologies for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds has attracted

much interest because of the shorter reaction time, mild reaction conditions, reduced energy consumption and higher product selectivity and yields (Scheme 34, Table 7).

Table 7. Catalyst-free synthesis of 1,8-dioxo-octahydroxanthenes under microwave

Compd. No.	R	Reaction condition	
		Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	C ₆ H ₅ -	2	92
2	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	2	95
3	2-ClC ₆ H ₄ -	3	91
4	3-ClC ₆ H ₄ -	2	88
5	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ -	2	94
6	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	3	84
7	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	3	89
8	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	3	85
9	4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	4	87

Scheme 34. Synthesis of 1,8-dioxo-octahydroxanthene.

Conclusion

MW-assisted chemical synthesis plays an important part in medicinal chemistry and pharmaceuticals such as drug discovery. Investigation into the possibility of using MW-irradiation to accelerate the rate and increase the yield of drug has been performed, especially drugs which are difficult to be prepared by using conventional methodology. The advantages of microwaves as a source of energy for heating synthesis reactions have been clearly demonstrated. This technique enables a number of reactions to be completed under mild reaction condition, in shorter reaction times, and with higher yields that either do not occur under conventional heating or occur at much higher temperatures. The future for the application of MW technology looks bright because of its efficiency and its potential to contribute to clean products. Microwave assisted synthesis provides a potential tool for synthetic chemistry in the glow of the current paradigm shift to "Green Chemistry".

Abbreviations

Cl: Chloro, °C: Degrees Celsius, DMF: Dimethyl Formamide, eq : Equivalent, F: Fluoro, GHz: Gigahertz, h: Hour, HIV: Human immunodeficiency virus, KBr: Potassium bromide, kcal: Kilocalorie, K₂CO₃: Potassium carbonate, KF: Potassium fluoride, Km: Kilometre, M: Mole, MAOS: Microwave-Assisted Organic Synthesis, MF: Molecular formula, mg: Milligram, MHz: Megahertz, ml: Milliliters, MW: Microwave, MWI: Microwave irradiation, NO₂: Nitro, nm: Nanometre, OH: Hydroxy, PAHs: Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, POCl₃: Phosphorus oxychloride, ppm: Parts per million, % : Percent, S: Second, W: Watt, ZnCl₂: Zinc Chloride.

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